

CASE-BASED LEARNING APPROACH: IT'S EFFECTS ON STUDENT'S ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND MOTIVATION IN CHEMISTRY

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Case-Based Learning Approach: It's Effects on Student's Academic Performance and Motivation in Chemistry

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Abstract

Case-based Learning approach is an instructional method that involves utilizing real-life scenarios and cases to engage students in active learning, critical thinking, and problem –solving within the context of Chemistry. Data will be collected through pre-and post-assessments, students surveys, and classroom observations to evaluate the effectiveness of the Case-based Learning Approach. A quasi-experimental design was employed where two intact classes exposed to CBLA and non-CBLA were administered a teacher-made test used to measure academic performance. Results of the study revealed that there is a high academic performance of students exposed to CBLA compared to the non-CBLA group. Furthermore, students exposed to CBLA significantly performed better than those exposed to non-CBLA. The findings of this research provided insights into the benefits of incorporating case-based learning in Chemistry education and its potential to enhance the overall learning experience. Results of the study revealed that students' level of motivation has a significant difference in students' motivation towards learning science in CBLA and non-CBLA as reflected by a t-value of -5.17 at 0.05 level. Thus, rejecting the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in the level of motivation of students as exposed to CBLA and those exposed to non-CBLA.

Keywords: *case-based, academic performance, motivation, and chemistry*

Introduction

Philippines' Grades 1-10 Science Curriculum envisions the development of scientifically, technologically, and environmentally literate and productive members of society. They must possess effective communication and interpersonal and lifelong learning skills as well as scientific values and attitudes. These skills will be acquired through a curriculum that focuses on knowledge relevant to real world and encompasses methods of inquiry. These will be implemented in a learning environment that promotes the construction of ideas and instills respect for others. The learning of science is also important for the nation's cultural development and preservation of its cultural identity. Science is most useful to a nation when it is utilized to solve its own problems and challenges, keeping a nation's cultural uniqueness and peculiarities intact. Thus in many countries, science teaching and learning is linked with culture (Department of Education, 2014).

Chemistry is undoubtedly one of the challenging science subjects. For first time encounters such as in Junior High School, the challenge is greater. Since many students have difficulty understanding the concepts and theories in this subject, they begin to lose interest in it. This lack of motivation in the subject eventually results in poor performance and low or failing grades. Hence, the burden of motivating and guiding the students to like the subject and enjoy the reality of the concepts tackled in class lies on the teachers.

Studies reveal that Filipino students have low retention of concepts, have limited reasoning and analytical skills, and poor communication skills (they cannot express ideas or explanations of events and phenomena in their own words) (UP NISMED, 2014). In addition, a large percentage of Grade 6 and fourth year students in selected schools cannot apply concepts to real-life problem solving situations nor design an investigation to solve a problem (UP NISMED, 2015). Many educators and graduate student researchers have identified several factors behind the low performance in science of Filipino students. These are: quality of teachers, the teaching-learning process,

The school curriculum, instructional materials, and administrative support (DOST-SEI, 2016). Grade 8 students in Malinao High School in Banisilan, North Cotabato are facing the same challenge in learning Chemistry. Their teachers are therefore faced with finding effective ways to make the subject matter realistic and interesting to them. It is notable that Malinao National High School has a fluctuating NAT result and has an average rating of 49.12% which is far from the Division target of 75% and has a gap difference of 25.88%.

In Case-based learning (CBL), students develop and apply course knowledge to solve a more tangible or actual "real life" problem. As we know that anyone is certainly more motivated to learn something that can be readily applied to the real world, it is easy to see why this method is so engaging. It has been an established method used through disciplines where students are made to apply their knowledge to real-world settings that promotes higher levels of understanding or cognition. CBL classes have students work in groups or pairs on case studies. Case studies are stories that involve one or more scenarios and characters. Each case deals with a specific problem in a certain area of study where students create solutions to such problems under the teacher's supervision (Herreid, 2013). CBL comprises guided inquiry and it is anchored in constructivism where the students are able to establish new meanings as they interact with their knowledge and their environment (Lee, 2012)

School students are naturally curious, which makes science an ideal subject for them to learn. Science allows students to explore their

world and discover new things. It is also an active subject, containing activities such as hands-on labs and experiments. This makes science well-suited to active younger children. Science is an important part of the foundation for education for all children. Thus, it is empirical to investigate the effects of case-based learning on students' academic performance and motivation in chemistry in Grade 8 High School students of Malinao, Banisilan, Cotabato.

Research Questions

This study evaluated the effects of CBLA on students' academic performance and motivation in Chemistry of Malinao High School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the students' level of academic performance when exposed to Case-based learning and non-case based learning in terms of:
 - 1.1. pretest; and
 - 1.2. posttest?
2. What is the level of students' motivation towards Chemistry as exposed to Case-based learning and those exposed to non- case based learning?
3. Is there a significant difference on students' academic performance as exposed to Case-based learning and those exposed to non- case based learning?
4. Is there a significant difference on student's level of motivation as exposed to Case-based learning and those exposed to non- case based learning?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quasi-experimental design where two intact classes to assess students' academic performance and motivation towards learning chemistry. One group was exposed to CBLA and another group to non-CBLA. A teacher-made test was administered to measure academic performance and a survey questionnaire.

Participants

The participants of this study were the 2 sections of Grade 8 students who were enrolled for the School Year of 2019-2020 at Malinao High School, Malinao, Banisilan, Cotabato. One group was exposed to Case-based learning approach and the other section was exposed to non-case-based learning approach.

Instruments

The researcher constructed a 100 test item questionnaire to determine the effects of case-based learning on students' academic performance in learning chemistry. The test instrument was subjected to reliability test and obtained a Cronbach's Alpha 0.83 indicating its reliability. To assess student's motivation the researcher adapted the modified MSLQ from Duncan & McKeachie (2005). There are 31 items in the Motivation Strategies divided in three components and six subscales. A range from 1 to 7 was considered.

Procedure

A letter was sent to the principal of Malinao High School asking permission to conduct the research study among the Grade 8 students for the school year 2019-2020. Upon the approval, the study was conducted in the third quarter that focused science discipline falls on chemistry with the topics namely: a. Particles nature of Matter b. Atoms: Inside Out, and c. Periodic table of an elements.

The pre-test was administered first to determine their prior knowledge of those topics and posttest followed after exposing them to case-based learning approach. The researcher handled and followed the Lesson Plan that was used in the course of this study.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of the study were still minors, an orientation of the study conducted with the parent and parent consent was obtained.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 presents the level of academic performance of students in their pre-test and posttest, frequency and percentage of scores of students exposed to case-based learning approach and non- case-based learning approach.

As shown, students' pretest scores under case-based learning approach obtained an overall mean score of 16.46% while students under non-case-based learning approach was 14.16% both indicating "Did Not Meet Expectation". The result is indicative of students in both groups having less prior knowledge on specified chemistry concepts considering that the topics are in spiral progression. This is supported by Berry (2008) when he pointed out that pre-test is administered prior to delivery of specific content or lesson where learners are not expected to know the presented concepts, thus, resulting to low scores.

Table 1. Students' pretest and posttest scores when exposed to case-based learning approach and non-case-based learning approach

Range	Case-Based Learning Approach				Non-Case –Based Learning Approach				Qualitative Interpretation
	Pretest		Posttest		Pretest		Posttest		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%	
90 – 100	0	0	16	35.56%	0	0	0	0	Outstanding (O)
85 - 89	0	0	20	44.44%	0	0	0	0	Very Satisfactory (VS)
80 – 84	0	0	3	6.67%	0	0	3	6.67%	Satisfactory (S)
75 – 79	0	0	4	8.89%	0	0	4	8.89%	Fairly Satisfactory (FS)
74 - below	45	100	2	4.44%	45	100	38	84.44%	Did Not Meet Expectation (DNME)
Total	45	100	45	100	45	100	45	100	
Overall MPS	16.46		88.64 (VS)		14.16		26.82 (DNME)		
Descriptive Rating	(DNME)				(DNME)				

Table 2 presents students' mean score and qualitative interpretation of students' motivation under intrinsic goal orientation exposed to case-based learning approach and non-case-based learning approach.

Table 2. Students' motivation under Intrinsic goal orientation

Intrinsic Goal Orientation Indicator	GROUP			
	CBL n=45		NON-CBL n=45	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
1. When I have the opportunity in this class, I choose course assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade	6.84	Highly Motivated	6.31	Highly Motivated
2. In chemistry class like this, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn	6.82	Highly Motivated	6.51	Highly Motivated
3. In chemistry class like this, I prefer course material that really challenges me so I can learn new things	6.80	Highly Motivated	6.51	Highly Motivated
4. The most satisfying thing for me in chemistry is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	6.76	Highly Motivated	6.58	Highly Motivated
Overall Mean	6.81	Highly Motivated	6.48	Highly Motivated

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

As reflected in the table, students exposed to case-based learning approach obtained a high mean score of 6.81 while students exposed to non-case-based learning approach obtained an overall mean score of 6.48 both indicated "Highly Motivated". The statements "When I have the opportunity in this class", "I choose course assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade" (6.84), "In chemistry class like this, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn" (6.82), "In chemistry class like this, I prefer course material that really challenges me so I can learn new things" (6.80). "The most satisfying thing for me in chemistry is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible" (6.76).

Table 3 presents students' mean score and qualitative interpretation of students' motivation under extrinsic goal orientation exposed to case-based learning approach and non-case-based learning approach.

Table 3. Students' motivation under extrinsic goal orientation

Extrinsic Goal Orientation Indicator	GROUP			
	CBL n=45		NON-CBL n=45	
	Mean	QI	Mean	QI
1. Getting a good grade in chemistry is the most satisfying thing for me right now.	6.89	Highly Motivated	6.49	Highly Motivated
2. I want to do well in this class because it is important to show my ability to my family, friends, or others.	6.78	Highly Motivated	6.56	Highly Motivated
3. The most important thing for me right now is improving my overall grade point average, so my main concern in this class is getting a good grade.	6.76	Highly Motivated	6.49	Highly Motivated
4. If I can, I want to get better grades in chemistry than most of the other students.	6.76	Highly Motivated	6.56	Highly Motivated
Overall Mean	6.74	Highly Motivated	6.52	Highly Motivated

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

As shown in the table, students exposed to case-based learning approach obtained an overall mean score of 6.74 and 6.52 for the non-case-based learning approach, both results indicate "Highly Motivated". This reveals that students are extrinsically motivated on the

following statements “Getting a good grade in chemistry is the most satisfying thing for me right now” (6.89), “I want to do well in this class because it is important to show my ability to my family, friends, or others” (6.78), “The most important thing for me right now is improving my overall grade point average, so my main concern in this class is getting a good grade” and “If I can, I want to get better grades in chemistry than most of the other students “ (6.76).

Table 4. *Students’ motivation under task value*

<i>Task Value</i>		<i>CBL n=45</i>		<i>NON-CBL n=45</i>	
		<i>Mean</i>	<i>QI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>QI</i>
1.	I think I will be able to use what I learn in chemistry in other courses.	6.86	Highly Motivated	6.56	Highly Motivated
2.	It is important for me to learn the course material in chemistry.	6.73	Highly Motivated	6.53	Highly Motivated
3.	I am very interested in the content area of chemistry	6.71	Highly Motivated	6.42	Motivated
4.	Understanding the subject matter of chemistry is very important to me	6.67	Highly Motivated	6.53	Highly Motivated
5.	I like the subject matter of chemistry.	6.69	Highly Motivated	6.54	Highly Motivated
6.	I think the course material in this chemistry class is useful for me to learn.	6.71	Highly Motivated	6.69	Highly Motivated
Overall Mean		6.72	Highly Motivated	6.56	Highly Motivated

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

Based on students’ pretest score under CBL obtained an overall mean score of 5.37 while students’ exposed to non-CBL obtained an overall mean score of 5.70 both groups indicate “Motivated” showed that learners are driven to go beyond their goals, focused on their learning with confidence in their own abilities keep improving their skills, and performing well. Students’ posttest score under CBL obtained 6.72 while students’ exposed to non-CBL have an overall mean score of 6.56 both groups indicate “Highly Motivated” results showed that learners are driven to go beyond their goals, more focused on their learning with great confidence in their own abilities, improving their skills and performing very well . It is noteworthy to point out that student’s value what they learn in science and finds interest in doing the tasks assigned to them by the teacher. The use of CBL gives students the opportunity to use their learnings to their everyday lives since examples of the cases provided to them are also happening in the real world setting, thus, the tasks are very relatable to them.

Table 5. *Students’ motivation under control learning beliefs*

<i>Control Learning Beliefs</i>		<i>GROUP</i>			
		<i>CBL n=45</i>		<i>NON-CBL n=45</i>	
<i>Indicator</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>QI</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>QI</i>
1.	If I try hard enough, then I will understand the course material.	6.73	Highly Motivated	6.47	Highly Motivated
2.	It is my own fault if I don't learn the material in Chemistry.	6.71	Highly Motivated	6.62	Highly Motivated
3.	If I don't understand the course material, it is because I didn't try hard enough.	6.71	Highly Motivated	6.40	Highly Motivated
4.	If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn the material in Chemistry	6.67	Highly Motivated	6.49	Highly Motivated
Overall Mean		6.71	Highly Motivated	6.49	Motivated

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

Based on students’ pretest score under CBL obtained an overall mean score of 5.33 while students’ exposed to non-CBL obtained an overall mean score of 5.37 both groups indicate “Motivated” results showed that learners are driven to go beyond their goals, focused on their learning with confidence in their own abilities keep improving their skills, and performing well. Students’ posttest score under CBL obtained 6.71 while students’ exposed to non-CBL have an overall mean score of 6.49 both groups indicate “Highly Motivated” showed that learners are driven to go beyond their goals, more focused on their learning with great confidence in their own abilities, improving their skills and performing very well . Learning beliefs play a vital role on how students may perform in class. As the data reveals, the students are well aware of the consequences of not taking the subject seriously, it is clearly suggesting that their motivational process will influence their actions and emotions on how they treat the subject as well as the course materials.

As shown, students exposed to case-based learning approach obtained an overall mean score of 6.65 and 6.46 for non-case-based learning approach both indicated “Highly Motivated”. This reveals that students exposure to the strategies employed were found in agreement with the following indicators: “I believe I will receive an excellent grade in Chemistry class” (6.76), “I’m certain I can master the skills “being taught in chemistry” (6.73), “I’m certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings

for this course” (6.71), “I expect to do well in chemistry class” and “I’m confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor in Chemistry” (6.69), “I’m confident I can learn the basic concepts taught in Chemistry”(6.58), “Considering the difficulty of this subject Chemistry, the teacher, and my skills, I think I will do well in this class” (6.53), and “I’m confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and tests in Chemistry (6.51).

Table 6. *Students’ motivation under self-efficacy for learning performance*

Self-Efficacy For Learning And Performance		GROUP			
		CBL n=45		NON-CBL n=45	
Indicator	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	
1. I believe I will receive an excellent grade in Chemistry class.	6.76	Highly Motivated	6.69	Highly Motivated	
2. I’m certain I can master the skills being taught in chemistry.	6.73	Highly Motivated	6.42	Highly Motivated	
3. I’m certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings for this course	6.71	Highly Motivated	6.40	Highly Motivated	
4. I expect to do well in chemistry class	6.69	Highly Motivated	6.33	Highly Motivated	
5. I’m confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor in Chemistry.	6.69	Highly Motivated	6.40	Highly Motivated	
6. I’m confident I can learn the basic concepts taught in Chemistry.	6.58	Highly Motivated	6.53	Highly Motivated	
7. Considering the difficulty of this subject Chemistry, the teacher, and my skills, I think I will do well in this class.	6.53	Highly Motivated	6.51	Highly Motivated	
8. I’m confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and tests in Chemistry	6.51	Highly Motivated	6.38	Highly Motivated	
Overall Mean	6.65	Highly Motivated	6.46	Highly Motivated	

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

Table 7. *Students’ motivation under test anxiety for learning performance*

Test Anxiety		GROUP			
		CBL n=45		NON-CBL n=45	
Indicator	Mean	QI	Mean	QI	
1. When I take a test in chemistry I think the consequence of failing	6.82	Highly Motivated	6.56	Highly Motivated	
2. I feel my heart beating fast when I take an exam in chemistry	6.80	Highly Motivated	6.38	Highly Motivated	
3. I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take an exam.	6.78	Highly Motivated	6.40	Highly Motivated	
4. When I take a test I think about items on other parts of the test I can't answer	6.73	Highly Motivated	6.36	Highly Motivated	
5. When I take a test in chemistry, I think about how poorly I am doing compared with other students	6.69	Highly Motivated	6.31	Highly Motivated	
Overall Mean	6.76	Highly Motivated	6.40	Highly Motivated	

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

As reflected in the table, students exposed to case-based learning approach obtained an overall mean score of 6.76 while students exposed to non-case-based learning approach got an overall mean score of 6.40 both indicating “Highly Motivated”. This means that each group are aware of test anxiety as a variable that may affect their performance toward learning chemistry and one of the factors that hinder them to get high score in answering questions and problems in chemistry.

Table 8. *Summary of students’ level of motivation in chemistry*

Motivation Indicators		CBL n=45		NON-CBL n=45	
		Mean	QI	Mean	QI
1. Intrinsic Goal Orientation	6.81	Highly Motivated	6.48	Highly Motivated	
2. Test Anxiety	6.76	Highly Motivated	6.52	Highly Motivated	
3. Extrinsic goal orientation	6.74	Highly Motivated	6.56	Highly Motivated	
4. Task value	6.72	Highly Motivated	6.49	Highly Motivated	
5. Control of Learning Beliefs	6.71	Highly motivated	6.46	Highly Motivated	
6. Self-Efficacy For Learning and Performance	6.65	Highly Motivated	6.40	Highly Motivated	
Overall Mean	6.73	Highly Motivated	6.48	Highly Motivated	

Legend: 6.01-7.00 Very True of me/Highly Motivated; 5.01-6.00 True of me/Motivated; 4.01-5.00 Moderately True of me/Moderately Motivated; 3.01-4.00 Somewhat True of me/Somewhat Motivated; 2.01-3.00 Slightly True of me/Less Motivated; 1.01-2.00 Not True of me/Not Motivated

As gleaned from the results this six points scale was adapted from Duncan and Mckechnie of 2005. Students exposed to case-based learning approach obtained an overall mean score of 6.73 while students' exposed in non-case-based learning is 6.48 both indicated "Highly Motivated" showed that learners are driven to go beyond their goals, more focused on their learning with great confidence in their own abilities, improving their skills and performing very well. towards learning chemistry. The following are the motivation indicators and their means in decreasing order: "Intrinsic goal orientation" (6.81), "Test anxiety" (6.76), "Extrinsic goal orientation" (6.74), "Task value" (6.72), "Control learning beliefs" (6.71), and "Self-efficacy for Learning and performance" (6.65).

Table 9. *Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on students' academic performance*

Group	N	(MPS)	SD		
CBL	45	39.89	4.97		
Non-CBL	45	30.72	11.29		
Total	90	70.61	6.98		
Source	SS	df	MS	F-value	Sig.
Group	29759.863	2	14879.932	235.874	.000*
Pre-test (Covariate)	1213.014	1	1213.014	19.228	.000*
Error	5488.331	87	63.084		
Total	520158.025	90			

As seen in the table, students exposed to case-based learning approach acquired a mean percentage score (MPS) of 88.64 (SD =4.97) while students exposed to non-case-based learning approach had a mean percentage score (MPS) 59.60 (SD= 11.29). The F-value is equal to 235.87 ($p < 0.05$) between groups indicating highly significant difference. Students exposed to CBL performed significantly higher as compared to non-CBL students, thus rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the academic performance of students' exposed to Case-based learning approach and those exposed to non-case -based learning.

Comparison of Students' Level of Science Motivation in Chemistry

Table 10 highlights the comparison between the levels of science motivation of students in CBL group from non-CBL group.

Table 10. *Comparison between the Levels of Motivation of the Students*

Motivation Indicators	Case-Based Learning Approach		Non-Case-Based Learning Approach		t	Sig.
	MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD		
1. Intrinsic goal orientation	6.81	.18	6.48	.27	-6.809	0.000*
2. Extrinsic goal orientation	6.74	.20	6.52	.23	-4.920	0.000*
3. Task value	6.72	.18	6.56	.23	-3.612	0.001
4. Control of Learning beliefs	6.71	.25	6.49	.29	-3.692	0.001
5 Test Anxiety						
6. Self-efficacy for learning and performance	6.76	.19	6.40	.30	-6.888	0.000*
	6.65	.16	6.46	.20	-5.071	0.000*
Overall Mean	6.73	(0.19)	6.48	(0.25)	-5.17	0.001

Results indicate significant difference between groups with values lower than 0.05. CBL group obtained an overall mean of 6.73 (SD=0.19) while non-CBL group obtained an overall mean of 6.48 (SD= 0.25). CBL group have significantly higher level of motivation than the non-CBL group. The null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the level of motivation of students' as exposed to Case-based learning approach and those exposed to non-case- based learning approach is rejected.

CBL as an instructional approach affected the motivation of students in learning Chemistry. The nature of CBL as a promising strategy geared towards the use of groups in solving case scenarios that have real life implications may be the contributing factor to this observation.

These results are consistent with the study of Dori and Herscovitz (1999) that case-based learning enhances students' motivation by displaying the significance of issue about real life situations. It also conforms to the study of Naumes & Naumes (2006) that case-based learning increases students' interest and enjoyment toward learning. Intrinsic interest or enjoyment and task value or usefulness are important reasons both for students being a part of the task and for enhancing their motivation.

This study examined the students' academic performance and motivation in Grade 8 Chemistry at Malinao High school utilizing the Case-Based Learning Approach. Specifically it aimed to describe the level of students' academic performance when exposed to CBLA and non-CBLA; identify the level of students' motivation when exposed to CBLA and those exposed to non-CBLA in terms of; intrinsic goal orientation, extrinsic goal orientation, task value, control of learning beliefs, self-efficacy for learning and performance, and test anxiety; ascertain the significant difference on students' academic performance when exposed to CBLA and those exposed to non-CBLA; find out the significant difference on students' level of motivation when exposed to CBLA and those exposed to non-CBLA.

Results of the study revealed that the mean percentage score (MPS) of students in CBLA and non-CBLA group in the pretest were 16.46% and 14.16% respectively, which indicate that both groups did not meet the set standard of the curriculum. However, the posttest mean percentage score of students exposed to CBLA was 88.64% indicating a “Very Satisfactory” performance thus, CBLA can develop the fundamental knowledge, skills, and understanding of the learners’ academic performance while students exposed to non-CBLA was 59.60% indicating “Did Not Meet Expectation”.

The CBLA students’ level of motivation towards Chemistry in terms of intrinsic goal orientation, extrinsic goal orientation, task value, and control of learning beliefs, self-efficacy for learning and performance, and test anxiety were also determined. were found to be ‘Highly motivated’ with an overall mean score of 6.73, while those exposed to non-CBLA were also found to be “Highly Motivated” with an overall mean score of 6.49.

The Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) on students’ academic performance indicates a significant difference between two groups. Further results indicate that students exposed to CBLA performed better than those exposed to non-CBLA with an F value equal to 235.87 at 0.05 level, thus rejecting the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on students’ academic performance when exposed to both groups.

There is a significant difference in students’ motivation towards learning science in CBLA and non-CBLA as reflected by a t-value of -5.17 at 0.05 level. Thus, rejecting the stated null hypothesis that there is no significant difference on the level of motivation of students’ as exposed to CBLA and those exposed to non-CBLA.

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based from the findings of the study.

The students’ academic performance under CBLA and non-CBLA similarly did not meet expectation on their pretest results. However, posttest results under CBLA improved to very satisfactory. On the contrary, those exposed to non-CBLA still did not meet expectation. Thus, exposure to CBLA may positively impact the performance of students.

On the level of motivation, students’ exposed to CBLA and non-CBLA were highly motivated on the six components of motivation toward learning chemistry. Hence, teachers need to continuously apply effective motivational drivers to keep the interest of students.

The students’ academic performance was significantly different between CBLA and non-CBLA group, rejecting the stated null hypothesis thus, CBLA can develop the fundamental knowledge, skills and automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.

The students’ level of motivation indicates significant difference between the two groups; hence, the study rejects the stated null hypothesis thus motivation of learners are driven to go beyond goals more focus on learning with great confidence with their abilities, improving their skills and performing very well.

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